

CHARACTERISATION OF INELASTIC PROCESSES IN CF TEXTILE REINFORCEMENTS

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1 General Introduction

Presently, the aerospace industry is looking into textile reinforcement for use in primary structural composites. This is mainly due to their relatively low price and improved hand ability and manufacturability. Moreover, due to their relatively high strength, thermal and electrical insulating properties, and fire resistance of some of the man-made fibres, today's commercial aircraft industry uses textile composites in the design and manufacture of many components in both interior panelling systems and secondary structures as well as in engine. As such, the development and use of textile fibre reinforced polymer composites for lightweight structures has become more and more important. Although all fibre reinforcement is produced as continuous fibre yarns, this is often not the form in which it is finally used in high performance applications. Common textile composites classified according to the fibre architecture include braided, woven, knitted, stitch, bonded and non-woven [1].

Manufacturing of composite components usually includes several steps, i.e. cutting the reinforcement, draping, impregnation of the dry deformable preform and curing. Draping of dry reinforcement plays a key role in terms of the subsequent composite manufacturing and the performance of the final product. During draping, a preform can be subjected to bending, shearing (including out-of-plane components) and compacting, or to combination of such loadings. In process simulation of a composite material, it is therefore essential to characterise the mechanical properties of the reinforcement itself [2]. The material data for the reinforcement may be then employed in subsequent composite manufacturing simulations. The understanding of mechanical properties of composites preforms is therefore important for composite manufacturing, and a fair amount of work

has gone into analysing these properties [3]. However, previous work on this topic has been limited to simple deformation modes and a restrictive choice of in-plane deformation mechanism. Another obstacle were the experimental methods incapable of characterising other than simple *in-plane* deformation modes. We are therefore presently lacking generic knowledge for the out-of-plane constitutive behaviour, and in particular for combined loading situations.

Measurement of the true stress-strain response of a material generally requires that a uniform state of stress and strain is realized in a gauge volume. While this can be done fairly easily with simple tension, all other states of stress and strain are considerably more difficult to obtain uniformly. In particular, many of the out-of-plane techniques in use are based on fixing the material between two parallel plates and either pushing the plates together or sliding them sideways at a constant plate separation. For example the compressive response of fiber networks and other porous solids has been studied extensively by simple compression between plates, and the nonlinear viscoelasticity of liquids is studied by sliding plate rheometry.

The basic parallel-plate concept has, however, one important disadvantage, the strain field near the free boundary is nonuniform in general, such that the measured stress is reduced compared to the infinite-sample limit. Also, the sample edge is often not representative of the bulk material, either due to surface flaws or due to the disruption of a large-scale microstructure [4,5]. These effects may be reduced by reducing free boundaries, e.g., by increasing the ratio of lateral dimensions to the height of the sample in a parallel plate geometry. On the other hand, a small plate separation combined with large plates may not always be possible for a given material and, moreover, demands precise parallelism, which may be difficult to attain. To

avoid these problems, the present work embraces a newly developed experimental equipment, consisting of a tri-axial rheometer for out-of-plane combined shear and compression testing.

This chief purpose of this work concerns characterisation of the constitutive inelastic frictional response of composites preforms when subjected to combinations of large out-of-plane deformations. The aim is to generate a generic understanding and a database for future constitutive model development. In consequence, both the internal and external responses developed within the preform and between a metallic tool and carbon fibre textile preforms when subjected to compression and out of plane shear is studied.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

Fig. 1. Quasi-UD reinforcement.

In the following study, a quasi-UD HexForce® G1157 D 1300 E01 2F, consisting of HTA 5131 6K unidirectional carbon fibres in warp direction, and EC9 34Z40 1383 glass fibres in weft direction has been used [6]. For the experiment, the material has been cut into quadratic pieces with the dimensions of 100x100 mm. The reinforcing textile is presented in Fig. 1. For one experiment, six layers of the reinforcement have been used.

2.2 Tri-axial rheometer

In a parallel plate geometry it is impossible to achieve a uniform state throughout the sample, due

to the inevitable free edges. However, under fairly general conditions there is an interior region away from edges, in which the state is approximately uniform.

Fig. 2. Schematic of sample deformation (the arrows indicate the relative motion of the plates): a) the resulting stress distribution $\sigma_{zz}(x)$ in compression, b) the resulting stress distribution $\sigma_{xz}(x)$ in shear.

As a start, consider the strain component due to compression in the x-direction, $u_{x,x}$, depends on the spatial coordinates x and z , Fig. 2 a. Hence, the compressive stress, $\sigma_{zz}(x)$, will not be constant since it is related to $u_{x,x}$ through Hooke's law. However, as the strain $u_{x,x}$ asymptotically approaches zero away from the edge, the stress will be nearly uniform in the interior of the pad. The compressive stress in the

pad was found to increase exponentially from the free edge inwards, to an asymptotic value σ_{zz}^{∞} far away from the edge:

$$\frac{\sigma_{zz}}{\sigma_{zz}^{\infty}} \approx 1 - \left(\frac{\nu}{1-\nu} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{x}{h} \sqrt{\frac{1-2\nu}{1-\nu}}}, \quad (1)$$

where h is the thickness. Roughly, the equation (1) states that a uniform state of uniaxial compression, with a negligible error in the stress (here within some 2%), is obtained in the region $x \geq h$.

Fig. 3. Tri-axial rheometer with a close up of the transducer head.

In shear, with a uniform relative tangential displacement on the upper and lower boundaries, the stress field will differ from pure shear as the free edges must be shear stress-free, resulting in a displacement field as illustrated in Fig. 2b. It can be shown that for a state of pure shear, in a semi-infinite pad, the upper bound for the shear stress decays exponentially with the distance x from the free boundary as:

$$\frac{\sigma_{xz}}{\sigma_{xz}^{\infty}} \approx \left(1 - e^{-\frac{x}{h} \sqrt{\frac{24}{1-\nu}}} \right). \quad (2)$$

Again the conclusion from equation (2) is that a uniform state is obtained for $x \geq h$, (the error is within 10-11 % at $x = h$).

In summary, the analysis of free edge effects suggests that a uniform state of stress and strain can be obtained in an inner region, beyond a sufficient distance from any free edges, a distance of roughly the sample thickness (Fig. 2).

The tri-axial rheometer instrument itself consists of a frame, a ball screw driven x,y -table, and a specially designed tri-axial stress transducer head (see Fig. 3). The sample is fixed between the transducer head and the x,y -table, acting as the upper and the lower plate, respectively. The relative position between the upper and lower plate and the x - and y -directions are measured discretely by on-board linear scales with a resolution of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$. The resolution of the stress transducer is about 10 Pa in compression and 1 Pa in shear. The development of the key component of the apparatus, the transducer head, is described in detail in [7] and is depicted in Fig. 2. The transducer head consists of two concentric transducer plates, a and b , attached to a base plate via the tri-axial load cells. The chief purpose of this arrangement is to absorb the free edge effect at transducer b and thus measure the true material stress response at transducer a . Fig. 2 illustrates the stress distribution in compression and shear. In consequence, if the sample is sufficiently thin, the stress distribution underneath transducer a will be uniform and the measurement will represent the true stress response of the material.

2.3 Contact friction

In the friction measurement, six layers of carbon fibre textile reinforcement with a total thickness of ca 3 mm are placed between the transducer head and the xy -moving metallic plate. The out-of-plane compression (z -direction) of 100, 250 and 500 N is applied at the speed of 1 mm/min, followed by shear in x and y plane directions, introduced to the bottom plate at two different speeds, 0.1 mm/min and 1 mm/min. Each sample is tested according to the following procedure; the sample is compressed to the prescribed z -force, then four shear cycles are applied (in x - and y -directions). The contact friction

between the sample and the metallic plate is then measured for four different samples.

2.4 Cyclic compression

Fig. 4. Velocity profile for a cyclic compression measurement.

During the cyclic compression, 20 layers of carbon fibre textile reinforcement with a total thickness of ca 8.5 mm are placed between the transducer head and the xy-moving metallic plate. The out-of-plane compression (z-direction) of 500 N is applied to the sample at the speed of 1 mm/min. The experiment is performed according to the following procedure; the sample is compressed to the prescribed z-force, followed by unloading to 0 N. The procedure is repeated five times. The cyclic compression is then measured for five different samples.

2.5 Cyclic shear

During the cyclic shear experiment, 20 layers of carbon fibre textile reinforcement with a total thickness of ca 8.5 mm are placed between the transducer head and the xy-moving metallic plate. The out-of-plane compression (z-direction) of ca 200 N is applied to the sample at the speed of 1 mm/min, followed by shear in x and y in-plane directions, introduced to the bottom plate at the speed of 1 mm/min. The experiment is performed according to the following procedure; the sample is compressed to the prescribed z-force, then five shear cycles are applied in x or y-directions. Four test in total are conducted, two in fibre direction (y-direction) and two transverse fibre direction (x-direction).

2.6 Shear modulus dependency on fibre volume fraction

In the shear modulus dependency on fibre volume fraction is characterised using 20 layers of carbon fibre textile reinforcement with a total thickness of ca 8.5 mm. The stack is placed between the transducer head and the xy-moving metallic plate. The out-of-plane compression (z-direction) of 100, 300 or 600 N is applied to the sample at the speed of 1 mm/min, followed by shear in x and y in-plane directions, introduced to the bottom plate at the speed of 1 mm/min. The shear modulus is measured for four different samples; two in x-direction and two in y-direction.

2.7 Relaxation experiments

During the relaxation test, 20 layers of carbon fibre textile reinforcement with a total thickness of ca 8.5 mm are placed between the transducer head and the xy-moving metallic plate. The sample is subjected to initial load (in z-direction) of 100, 300, 600 or 900 N followed by a relaxation for 10 minutes at constant deformation. During the relaxation the force decreases with time. One relaxation experiment is performed for each load level.

3 Results

3.1 Contact friction

Fig. 5. Results from the contact friction measurement at $Z=100, 250$ and 500 N for one specimen.

The representative curves from the contact friction measurements are presented in Fig. 5. It is observed that the friction values for most of the experiments is about 0.5, and is independent of pre-stress. The averaged results from the four shear cycles applied

in x- and y-in-plane directions for z= 100, 250 and 500 N are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Average friction results.

Sample No.	Friction x (-)			Friction y (-)		
	100	250	500	100	250	500
Z (N)	100	250	500	100	250	500
1	0.49	0.51	0.49	-	0.52	0.49
2	0.52	0.49	0.44	0.55	0.45	0.40
3	0.44	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.52	0.46
4	0.54	0.47	0.44	0.51	0.43	0.39

a)

b)

Fig. 6. Experimental results from cyclic compression: stress vs. fibre volume fraction a) result from one experiment, b) combined results log-log plot.

3.2 Cyclic compression

Experimental results on cyclic compression are presented in Figure 6. It is observed that after the first compression cycle, the hysteresis decreases in relation to both time and displacement. This may indicate a fibre rearrangement and collapse of the fibrous network in the first cycle into a stable configuration. In order to summarise the experimental data, the results has been fitted to the so called van Wyk equation

$$\sigma_n = k_{vol}(\phi^\beta - \phi_0^\beta), \tag{3}$$

where σ_n is the normal out-of-plane stress, k_{vol} is a constitutive front factor, ϕ is the fibre volume fraction, ϕ_0 is the fibre volume fraction is unloaded configuration and β is an exponent. The results are summarised in Table 2, fitting is performed separately for the first and the subsequent cycles. The fibre volume fraction in unloaded configuration is found to be $\phi_0 = 0.4$. An interesting observation is the increase of exponent from 12 to 17, which indicates increased parallelism in the fibre network [8].

Table 2. Summary of the compressive response.

Parameter	First cycle	Subsequent cycles
k_{vol} [Pa]	10^9	10^8
β	12	17

3.3 Cyclic shear

Experimental results on cyclic shear are presented in Figure 7 for x-direction (perpendicular fibre direction) and in Figure 8 for y-direction (parallel fibre direction). It is observed that the response in x-direction (transverse fibres) is significantly different than the response in y-direction. In particular, the response transverse fibres is less dissipative, while the response parallel fibres exhibits nearly elastic ideal-plastic behaviour. This may be addressed by the fact that the fibres entangle more easily in transverse direction, while they slide along the fibre direction. Also, the elastic response along fibre direction is stiffer in the elastic regime then the response transverse fibres. The opposite is true in the plastic regime, where the transverse network is capable of build up plastic (frictional) stresses. It is also evident that the response in y-direction

dissipates more energy than in x-direction. One again, this may indicate a more developed plastic (frictional) effects parallel the fibres. Finally, all the cycles dissipates similar amount of energy independent of direction the is little or no degradation of the elastic response meaning that the fibre network is able to rebuild and rearrange on shear.

Fig. 7. Experimental results from cyclic shear measurements in x-direction: a) force vs. time, b) stress vs. strain.

Fig. 8. Experimental results from cyclic shear measurements in y-direction: a) force vs. time, b) stress vs. strain.

3.4 Shear modulus

The experimental results from shear modulus characterisation are presented in Figure 9 for x-

direction and in Figure 10 for y-direction. The resulting data is for different volume fraction fibres. It is observed that the shear response is increasing for increasing volume fraction. It is evident from the results that the stress response due to applied shear strain is increasing (stiffening) at higher volume fractions. It appear that the behaviour, in concordance with the compressive behaviour, follows the power law. Moreover, it is observed that the response in x-direction (transverse the fibres) is significantly stiffer than the response in y-direction. It is also evident that the response in y-direction dissipates more energy than in x-direction. Once again, this may indicates a more developed plastic (frictional) effects parallel the fibres. We believe that it is caused by the fibres sliding along each other in fibre direction and entangle perpendicular the fibre direction.

Fig. 9. Experimental results from shear modulus characterisation in x-direction: stress vs. strain. given at volume fraction 0.468, 0.538 and 0.625.

In order to summarise the experimental data, we have chose to relate the elastic response against the fibre volume fraction. In summary, the average tangential modulus in the elastic region ($|\epsilon| \leq 0.01$) is presented as a function of ϕ , the fibre volume fraction. Since, the elastic stiffness in the first cycle was significantly different from the subsequent cycles we present these results separately. Here G_r is the "relaxed" stiffness in from the first cycle and G_d is the "dynamic" stiffness taken as an average from the subsequent cycles. The results are presented in Table 3 and 4, where ϕ is the fibre volume fraction, G_r is the relaxed modulus, G_d is the dynamic modulus, ϵ_p is the strain at elastic limit.

Fig. 10. Experimental results from shear modulus characterisation in y-direction: stress vs. strain. given at volume fraction 0.468, 0.538 and 0.625.

Table 3. The shear response in X-direction.

ϕ	G_r [Pa]	G_d [Pa]	ϵ_p
0.468	$1.45 \cdot 10^5$	$2.175 \cdot 10^5$	0.045
0.538	$4.8 \cdot 10^5$	$7.81 \cdot 10^5$	0.08
0.625	$1.315 \cdot 10^6$	$2.42 \cdot 10^6$	0.15

Table 4. The shear response in Y-direction.

ϕ	G_r [Pa]	G_d [Pa]	ϵ_p
0.468	$2.125 \cdot 10^5$	$3.564 \cdot 10^5$	0.02
0.538	$5.816 \cdot 10^5$	$2.077 \cdot 10^6$	0.025
0.625	$1.837 \cdot 10^6$	$4.62 \cdot 10^6$	0.05

Since it is expected [8] that the shear behaviour will also follow the van Wyk power law type of response, the data in Tables 3 and 4 has been fitted to the following equation

$$G_d = k_{iso} \cdot \phi^\alpha, \quad (4)$$

and the results presented in Table 5 and Figure 11.

Table 5. Summary of the compressive response.

Parameter	X direction	Y direction
k_{iso} [Pa]	$1.25 \cdot 10^8$	$5.6 \cdot 10^8$
α	8.32	9.5

Fig. 11. The shear stiffness as a function of fibre volume fraction.

3.5 Relaxation

The representative curves from the relaxation experiments are presented in Fig. 12-14. It is observed that all the specimens, independent of the initial load, dissipate similar amount of stress; approximately 40%. This indicates a viscoelastic material behaviour as well as plastic (frictional and in particular lubricated contact) effects. At the present state of research, we believe that it is caused by the sizing applied onto the fibres.

Fig. 12. Relaxation results presented as force vs. time.

Fig. 13. Relaxation results presented stress vs. strain.

Fig. 14. Relaxation results presented stress vs. strain.

4 Concluding remarks

The experimental results clearly indicate development of intrinsic frictional as well as lubricated contact within the fibrous preforms. As a main result, this study shown that the out-of-plane shear response follows the van Wyk power law type of behaviour. In addition, we were able to conclude that a typical aeronautic grade preform is viscoelastic. At the present state of research, we believe that it is caused by the sizing applied onto the fibres. In consequence, additional testing to remove this effect are being performed. Also, we were able to conclude that the preform is stiffer in transverse direction than along fibres in shear. Another interesting result is the fact that the preform is nearly elastic ideal plastic along fibres and

elastoplastic transverse the fibres. This may be contributed to the fact that the fibre network form more easily transverse the fibre direction. In comparison, along the fibres the response is almost elastic ideal plastic. This indicate that the internal friction develops there due to fibres sliding over one other.

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